

ANASTOMOTIC COMPLICATIONS AMONG CARCINOMA ESOPHAGUS PATIENTS UNDERGOING ESOPHAGECTOMY IN A TERTIARY CARE CENTRE

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18081039>

Keywords

Anastomotic leak, Stenosis, McKeown esophagectomy, Ivor Lewis esophagectomy, Morbidity and mortality

Article History

Received on 04 July 2025

Accepted on 15 July 2025

Published on 19 July 2025

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the incidence and impact of different anastomotic complications on morbidity and mortality in patients undergoing esophagectomy for esophageal carcinoma (EC)

Study Design: Cross-Sectional Prospective Study.

Study Setting: Department of Thoracic Surgery, Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre, Karachi

Study Duration: Twelve Months (January to December'23).

Methodology: The study reviewed 60 patients, comprising 32 males and 28 females with a mean age of 46.33 ± 14.31 years. Thirty patients each underwent Ivor Lewis (ILE) and McKeown (MKE) esophagectomy, selected based on the anatomical site of the tumor. Data regarding demographics, tumor characteristics, and postoperative outcomes were recorded and analyzed.

Results: Squamous cell carcinoma (75%) was the most common histological variant. The overall complication rate was 36.7% (n=22), with anastomotic leaks occurring in 20% (n=12) of patients. The leak rate was significantly higher in the MKE group (33.3%, n=10) compared to ILE (6.7%, n=2). Hand-sewn anastomosis in MKE was significantly associated with increased leak risk (p=0.006). Statistical analysis identified tumor length >5 cm (p=0.02), neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy (p=0.02), male gender (p=0.02), age >45 years (p=0.04), tumor wall thickness (p=0.019), and nutritional deficiency as significant risk factors. The overall mortality rate was 11.7% (n=7). Notably, 85% of mortalities occurred in the ILE group, largely attributed to cardiopulmonary compromise (66.6%) rather than leaks alone.

Conclusion: Anastomotic complications remain a major challenge after esophagectomy. MKE; particularly hand-sewn anastomosis is associated with higher leak rates. While, ILE demonstrates lower leak rates, ILE may carry a higher mortality risk largely attributable to patient-related factors rather than surgical technique.

INTRODUCTION

The incidence of esophageal carcinoma (EC) has escalated with over 604,000 patients reported globally in 2020 with subsequent mortalities in 544,100 cases.¹ It constitutes the seventh most prevalent malignancy globally and sixth leading cause of cancer related fatalities.² Pakistan has an overall incidence of 4.1 per 100,000 with majority cases documented from Balochistan.³ The disease commonly manifests between the ages of 50 and 70, with a higher prevalence in males.⁴ However, in Pakistan, cases have been reported across a wider age range (15–92 years), with an average age of 49 years.³ Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) and adenocarcinoma (ADC) are the two primary histological subtypes.⁵ SCC is the most common subtype in Asian population, primarily affecting upper two-third thoracic esophagus. In contrast, ADC is more prevalent in Western nations, typically involving distal esophagus. Risk factors linked to SCC includes achalasia, tobacco, alcohol, caustic injury, Plummer-Vinson syndrome, poor diet, low social status and Zenker diverticulum whereas, Barrett's esophagus, gastroesophageal reflux disease, obesity and tobacco are associated with ADC.⁶ The mainstay of surgical management of EC is esophagectomy, a complex surgical procedure requiring adequate preoperative optimization and meticulous surgical technique.⁷ Ivor Lewis-two stage (ILE), McKeown- three stage (MKE) and Transhiatal (THE) esophagectomy are among the common surgical modalities; performed by either open or minimally invasive techniques.⁸ Esophagectomy carries a significant risk of complications such as anastomotic leak, stenosis, hoarseness, etc. Out of all, anastomotic leakage (AL) is the most dreadful complication, substantially contributing to increased morbidity and mortality.⁹ MKE has a five-fold higher rate of anastomotic leaks as compared to ILE but generally well tolerated. In contrast, leak from thoracic anastomoses tends to be more morbid.¹⁰ Several factors influence esophageal anastomotic integrity; location of anastomoses (cervical or intrathoracic), technique (single vs double layered; hand sewn vs stapled), type of conduit (stomach, jejunum or colon), tumor stage, proximity to tumor and neoadjuvant radiotherapy or chemotherapy.⁸

Despite the rising incidence of EC in Pakistan, indigenous literature addressing complications of esophagectomy remains scarce. A study conducted by Shafiq et al in 2020 reported a 5.1% incidence of AL with a mortality rate of 13.3% in affected patients.¹¹ Given this gap, the present study aims to expand local literature by analyzing postoperative anastomotic complications among EC patients undergoing esophagectomy for EC and to identify factors influencing these outcomes.

METHODOLOGY:

This prospective descriptive study was conducted at the Department of Thoracic Surgery, Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Center, Karachi, from January to December 2023 after ethical approval (No: F.2-81/2022-GENL/328/JPMC). Patients with esophageal carcinoma who underwent esophagectomy during the study period were included after informed consent, while those without postoperative complications were excluded. Patients were followed for up to twelve months to assess anastomotic complications, primarily leakage and stenosis. Treatment was guided by tumor histology and staging. Patients with squamous cell carcinoma received neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy according to the CROSS protocol, whereas adenocarcinoma patients received perioperative chemotherapy using FLOT-4 or MAGIC regimens. Preoperative staging was performed using contrast-enhanced CT, endoscopic ultrasound, and PET-CT when indicated, with tumors classified according to AJCC 8th edition TNM staging. Patients underwent either McKeown or Ivor Lewis esophagectomy based on tumor location. Cervical anastomosis in McKeown procedures was performed using hand-sewn or linear-stapled techniques, while intrathoracic anastomosis in Ivor Lewis procedures was constructed using a circular stapler. Data on demographics, tumor characteristics, surgical details, and postoperative outcomes were recorded. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with results expressed as means, frequencies, and percentages. Associations were assessed using the chi-square test, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Sixty patients were included (53.3% males), with a mean age of 46.3 ± 14.3 years and mean BMI of 20.6 ± 2.4 kg/m². Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) was the predominant histology (75%), while adenocarcinoma (ADC) accounted for 23.3%. The distal thoracic esophagus was the most common tumor site (50%). SCC mainly involved the middle thoracic esophagus and was significantly associated with smoking and low socioeconomic status, whereas ADC exclusively involved the distal esophagus and showed a strong association with GERD.

Neoadjuvant therapy was administered to 76.6% of patients, primarily SCC cases treated under the CROSS protocol, while all ADC patients received perioperative chemotherapy. Half of the patients underwent Ivor Lewis esophagectomy (ILE) and half McKeown esophagectomy (MKE). Overall complications occurred in 36.7%, with anastomotic leak in 20%, significantly higher after MKE than ILE. Leaks were associated with tumor length >5 cm, neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy, male gender, age >45 years, increased wall thickness, nutritional deficiency, prolonged operative time, and blood loss >500 ml. All MKE leaks followed hand-sewn anastomosis and were linked to longer hospital stay, while both ILE patients who developed leaks died.

DISCUSSION:

Esophagectomy remains the primary surgical treatment for esophageal carcinoma, but anastomotic complications continue to be a major source of postoperative morbidity and mortality. In this study, squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) was the predominant histological subtype (75%) with male predominance, consistent with reports from developing regions.^{1,2,14} Notably, patients presented at a younger age compared with regional data, with a higher proportion under 30 years, a trend also reported in limited South Asian studies.^{3,15}

The overall anastomotic leak (AL) rate of 20% was comparable to published literature.^{16,17} However, leaks were significantly more frequent following McKeown esophagectomy than Ivor Lewis procedures, supporting evidence that cervical

anastomosis carries a higher leak risk than intrathoracic anastomosis.^{16,18}

Several patient- and tumor-related factors were significantly associated with AL, including male gender, age >45 years, smoking, diabetes, nutritional deficiency, neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy, prolonged operative time, and increased blood loss, findings consistent with previous studies.^{18,19,22,24} Notably, tumor length and wall thickness emerged as significant predictors of AL, factors that have not been well explored in earlier literature and warrant further investigation.

Anastomotic leakage was strongly associated with subsequent stenosis and prolonged hospital stay, as previously described.^{5,8,10} Mortality was higher in intrathoracic leaks compared to cervical leaks, reflecting the greater clinical severity of thoracic contamination.^{7,13} Despite the higher leak rate in McKeown procedures, most cervical leaks were managed conservatively with acceptable outcomes, whereas mortality following Ivor Lewis esophagectomy was largely related to advanced disease and patient factors rather than surgical technique alone.¹⁰

Anastomotic complications remain a significant challenge following esophagectomy for esophageal carcinoma, with anastomotic leak being a major contributor to postoperative morbidity and mortality. McKeown esophagectomy, particularly with hand-sewn cervical anastomosis, was associated with a higher leak rate, whereas Ivor Lewis esophagectomy demonstrated lower leak incidence but higher mortality, largely related to patient and disease factors.

CONCLUSION:

Tumor characteristics, nutritional status, neoadjuvant therapy, and operative factors significantly influenced anastomotic integrity. Careful patient selection, preoperative optimization, and meticulous surgical technique are essential to reduce postoperative complications. Larger, multicenter studies are required to validate these findings and refine strategies for risk reduction.

Table: Baseline Characteristics, Treatment Details, Surgical Procedures, and Postoperative Outcomes of Esophageal Carcinoma Patients (N = 60)

Category	Variable	n (%) / Mean ± SD
Demographics	Age (years)	46.33 ± 14.31
	≤30 years	11 (18.3%)
	Male	32 (53.3%)
	Female	28 (46.7%)
	BMI (kg/m ²)	20.6 ± 2.40
Risk Factors & Comorbidities	Smoking	36 (60.0%)
	Poor dietary habits	36 (60.0%)
	Low socioeconomic status	32 (53.3%)
	GERD	14 (23.3%)
	Diabetes mellitus	15 (25.0%)
Tumor Characteristics	Hypertension	11 (18.3%)
	Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC)	45 (75.0%)
	Adenocarcinoma (ADC)	14 (23.3%)
	Upper thoracic esophagus	12 (20.0%)
	Middle thoracic esophagus	18 (30.0%)
Disease Stage	Distal thoracic esophagus	30 (50.0%)
	Limited disease	22 (36.7%)
	Locally advanced disease	35 (58.3%)
Neoadjuvant / Adjuvant Therapy	Advanced disease	2 (3.3%)
	Neoadjuvant therapy (overall)	46 (76.6%)
	CROSS protocol (SCC)	36 (60.0%)
	MAGIC regimen (ADC)	10 (33.3%)
Surgical Procedure	FLOT4 regimen (ADC)	4 (13.3%)
	Ivor Lewis esophagectomy (ILE)	30 (50.0%)
	McKeown esophagectomy (MKE)	30 (50.0%)
Type of Anastomosis	Hand-sewn cervical	20 (33.3%)
	Linear stapled cervical	10 (16.7%)
	Circular stapled (intrathoracic)	30 (50.0%)
Postoperative Complications	Any complication	22 (36.7%)
	Wound infection	20 (33.3%)
	Anastomotic leak	12 (20.0%)
	Anastomotic stenosis	13 (21.7%)
	Hoarseness	6 (10.0%)
	Mechanical ventilation	11 (18.3%)
Anastomotic Leak Details	Leak in MKE	10 (33.3%)
	Leak in ILE	2 (6.7%)
	Hand-sewn leaks (MKE)	10 (100%)
	Post-leak stenosis	9 (75.0%)
Outcomes	Mortality (overall)	7 (11.7%)
	Mortality after AL	3 (25.0%)
	Mortality in ILE with AL	2 (100%)
	Mortality in MKE with AL	1 (10.0%)

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